
APPLICATION, CHEMICAL COMPONENT AND THE BIOREFINERY OF IPOMOEA BATATAS WASTES TO SUGAR

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ABSTRACT

Sweet potato starch was converted to sugar through bio-production. Also, the proximate analysis was performed on the peel, and the results indicated that it contained adequate amounts of starch and total sugars to enable it to be used as a biomass feedstock for bio-ethanol production. In Method 1, the merged sweet potatoes were hydrolysed by sodium hydroxide solution and in Method 2, the peels were hydrolysed by hydrochloric acid at a different concentration and temperature to obtain maximum starch conversion. **Objective:** In this study, method 1 involves the conversion of starch from Ipomoea batatas to sugar in form of a syrup which are used for consumption. In addition, Ipomoea batatas peel wastes are used in method 2 to produce ethanol. The results of this study indicate that sweet potato peel, a waste product, may be used as a feedstock for the production of bioethanol.

Keywords: Sweet Potato, Sugar, Starch, Bioethanol, Hydrolysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

With an ever-increasing global population, the need for chemical energy has grown steadily throughout time. Today, the need for energy for transporting, heating, and processing is on the rise, and environmental concerns [2] are becoming more prevalent. Alternative fuel research is also being supported by government controls on exhaust pollution, rising costs for petroleum-based fuels, and the expected depletion of global petroleum supplies in the near future [1]. For diesel engines, alternative fuels such as ethanol and methanol have been examined and evaluated. There is a significant influence on the environment due to the yearly use of nearly 30 billion barrels of oil. Energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources have been implemented as a means of maintaining a healthy environment while also fulfilling the rising demand for energy. Bio-ethanol refers to ethanol produced from renewable sources and used as fuel or as a fuel additive.[3] Fermentation is a microbiological process that produces bio-ethanol, one of several renewable energy sources. Simple sugars are transformed to ethanol and carbon (IV) oxide by microbes in this process, although ethanol may also be chemically generated by combining ethylene with steam. Oxygenating the fuel mixture is one of the primaries uses for the fuel additive ethanol, which may be used as a petrol alternative in cars. Many European nations employ bio-ethanol as a fuel option that is up to 15 percent [4] more efficient than gasoline. When potatoes are processed, they produce a lot of waste. About one-fourth of the potatoes that enter the facility are wasted. Yeast may utilize these wastes as carbon sources during alcohol fermentation to make bio-ethanol from them. Farmers in Minnesota create an estimated 400,000 tonnes of waste potatoes each year, and many of these wastes are sold at a low price in order to be fed to their livestock, [5,6,7] while others are allowed to decompose and become fertilizer. Because of its high content of starch and sugars that may be used to produce alcohol, potato peel is an ideal feedstock for this process [9,10].

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials and Samples

Sweet potatoes were bought at the open market. 6kg of sweet potatoes were peeled and weighed. The edible portion of the sweet was used for sugar conversion, while the peel was used for proximate analysis. The sweet potato's edible portion and the peel were weighed separately. After washing, the peels were dried.

Method 1

2.2 Milling of the Edible Sweet Potatoes

The potatoes were washed, peeled, and bad parts were cut off and thrown away. The potatoes were then cut into smaller pieces and boiled for about 20 minutes.

After boiling, the potatoes were mashed. To turn the extracted starch into a liquid, it was blended well.

2.3 Conversion of starch to sugar: Syrup

In this step, the researcher obtained sugar as a syrup, which can be light brown in colour. The extracted starch was blended well in order to convert it into a liquid form. After that, it was put into a sieve and the liquid was filtered. Normally the liquid which was extracted is a rich source of potassium. The starch was washed along with water and the washed starch was put into a vessel. It was kept for about one day so that the Starch could be obtained from the above method. The starch was poured into a vessel and water was added in order to hydrate. At this point, the PH was examined, and the PH was indicated as 6.3. HCL/H₂SO₄ was added to the solution in order to convert it into 1.5 PH. Then the potato mixtures were added into smaller jars. After that, the lids were closed and placed into the pressure cooker. It was kept inside the pressure cooker for about 2 hrs. After the 2hrs, the gelatinous liquid appeared as a clear solution, therefore, the liquid was poured into a larger pan. Next, it was neutralized with NaOH, and after stirring it for about 30-45 minutes, the syrup was formed. Then the syrup too was filtered well in order to remove any waste/ undiluted particles.

Method 2

2.3 Analysis of proximity

2.3.1 Moisture content and dry matter determination

By drying the sample at 105°C to a fixed weight, the moisture content may be analyzed. Peel was withdrawn from oven for 30 minutes to cool in desiccators, then weighed, and returned to oven for drying for another 16 hours. After one hour, the peel was removed from the oven, cooled in the desiccators, and weighed again until a constant weight of dried potato samples was produced. As soon as the dry weight remained steady, the peels were taken out of the oven.

2.3.2 Calculation of the total ash and organic materials in a given sample

The amount of organic and mineral matter in sweet potato peel was calculated using the total ash. Crude sweet potato peel samples were weighed in a crucible and the crucible's weight was recorded. The crucible containing the sample was placed in a preheated furnace. The furnace temperature was gradually increased from 250°C to 450°C every 20 minutes to prevent incomplete ashing. After an hour of ashing, the crucible was taken from the furnace and placed in desiccators for cooling. One hour of cooling and weighing followed by the sample crucible were the steps taken.

2.3.3 Fat analysis

Muslin cloth that was free of fat was weighed; the weighed pieces of muslin material were added to the mixture. The 500ml round bottom flask was weighed after being washed and dried. The flask was filled up to two-thirds of the way with petroleum ether, and the Soxhlet extractor was used to extract the ether. The heat source was set so that the solvent (petroleum ether) boiled gradually and was permitted to syphon for six hours. The muslin cloth was taken from the condenser. After that, the petroleum ether was purified through the process of distillation. At 100°C for 5 minutes, the flask holding the fat residue was oven dried. The flask was desiccated, cooled, then weighed when it had dried out. Weighed the muslin after it had been dried in the oven at 500C for a period of time.

2.3.4 Determination of the Sugar Reduction Factor

Sugars included in sweet potato peel, hydrolyzed peel, cellulose-degraded sweet potato peel, and fermented peels were all measured for reducing power. We weighed 80 millilitres of water, 20 millilitres of anhydrous sodium carbonate, 2.5 grammes of potassium sodium tartrate, 2 grammes of sodium hydrogen carbonate, and 2.5 grammes of anhydrous sodium carbonate to make 100 millilitres. Drizzled into a little amount of water, 15g copper sulphate was added. 100ml of sulphuric acid had been added to the solution. Sulphuric acid and ammonium molybdate were dissolved in 45ml water and 2.5ml of sulfuric acid was added. Disodium hydrogen arsenate (0.3g) was dissolved in 25ml of distilled water and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. By diluting 100ml with 1g of glucose, the standard glucose solution was created. It was created by adding 1 ml of glucose solution to 100 ml of water and diluting it to a concentration of 100 nM. Five well-labeled test tubes were used to measure out 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0ml of a working standard. A test tube marked "blank" was filled with 1 cc of water. Three beakers were filled with 0.1g of each test sample, which was then weighed. Each beaker received 100 ml of distilled water. Four test tubes were filled with 1 ml of the test samples. The first five test

tubes were filled with 1 ml of distilled water, 1 ml of alkaline copper tartrate reagent, and 1 ml of shaking for adequate mixing. For 10 minutes, the test tubes were cooked and then cooled in a water bath. Each test tube was filled with 1ml of arsenomolybdate reagent and shook thoroughly. Finally, each test tube was filled with 10ml of distilled water by adding 7ml of distilled water. The spectrometer was connected and set to 620nm wavelength. The spectrometer measured the blue color absorption in each sample. To figure out how much reducing sugar there is, a graph of absorbance against concentration was made.

2.4 Total carbohydrates and starch Analysis

To make anthrone reagent, 0.1g anthrone was added to 100ml of ice-cold 95% H₂SO₄ solution. 0.1ml glucose was diluted to 100ml with 100ml of distilled water to make a standard glucose solution for testing. Stock solution was made by diluting 10 millilitres of working standard glucose solution by the same volume of distilled water. In order to make each sample solution, 0.1 grammes of the test samples were added to 100 mL of water. Five well-labeled test tubes were filled with 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0ml of a working standard each. In a test tube marked "blank," 1 ml of water was measured out and put in. Sweet potato peel hydrolysate, cellulose-degraded sweet potato peel solution was all measured into three test tubes at a concentration of 1 ml each. The first five test tubes contained 1ml of distilled water, which was added to each of the test tubes individually. Each test tube was filled with 4 ml of anthrone reagent and shaken to ensure a correct mix before being analyzed. They were boiled for 8 minutes in an oven and then cooled down in water. The spectrometer was attached and tuned to 620nm wavelength. The spectrometer was used to measure the absorbance of the green color in each of the specimens. Reducing sugar content was determined by plotting the graph of green color absorbance vs concentration in each test tube.

2.5 Hydroxylation of starch

It is necessary to perform hydrolysis before fermenting starchy materials in order to break down amylopectin and amylose interactions into fermentable sugars. Enzymes and acids may both be used for starch hydrolysis. Acid hydrolysis, also known as chemical hydrolysis, is a hydrolysis process that uses acid to break down starch into fermentable sugars. Hydrolysis uses acid to break down α - 1,4 - glycosidic bonds, resulting in glucose units. Hydrochloric acid was used in this study to break down the materials into sugars that could be used for fermentation.

First Experiment

NH₄NO₃ and peptone were added to each of the conical flask containing 40g of sample, and the flasks were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Each flask was filled with 120ml of HCL 0.2M, 0.5M, 1.0M, 2.0M, sequentially. Afterward, the flasks were placed in an autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes to disinfect the solutions within.

Second Experiment

For this experiment, the sample was measured into three conical flasks that contained 40g each. The flasks contained 5ml of NH₄NO₃ (0.5 percent), 1ml of peptone (0.1 percent), and 120ml of HCL0.5M. For 15 minutes, the autoclave sterilized each of the mixtures in the flasks at 121°C. Fermentable sugars were created during the sterilizing process by breaking down the starch. Flasks were cooled for 40 minutes, reducing sugar content was calculated, and the pH meter was used to adjust the sample to 4.15 using NaOH, as shown in Figure 2.

Third Experiment

In five 250ml Conical flasks, 40g of sample was measured with 5ml of 0.5% NH₄NO₃, 1ml of 0.1% peptone, and 120ml of H 0.5M. For 15 minutes, the autoclave sterilized each of the solutions in the flasks at 121°C. A total of 40 minutes were given for the flasks to cool down completely. The starch was broken down into fermentable sugars during sterilization, and the amount present was assessed.

Fourth Experiment

In five 250ml Conical flasks, 40g of sample was measured with 5ml of 0.5% NH₄NO₃, 1ml of 0.1% peptone, and 120ml of H 0.5M. The autoclave was used to sterilize each of the mixtures in the flasks for 15 minutes at 121°C. A total of 40 minutes were given for the flasks to cool down completely. It was determined that the quantity of fermentable sugars present in the starch during sterilization was studied. The hydrolysate's pH was enhanced.

Production of ethanol from fermented hydrolyzed Ipomoea batatas peel

Fermentation durations for the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* were modified for each set of starch hydrolysate.

During the 48-hour fermentation process, the starch hydrolysates generated from acid hydrolysis were also exposed to different temperatures, pH, and inoculum concentrations.

Fifth Experiment

Fermentation was carried out on starch hydrolysates from all other sets, except for experimental run 1. Each flask was loaded with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* after it was collected. Temperature of 32.5°C and a pH of 5.0 were used to promote fermentation. 6 percent (v/v) of the inoculum was used, and the fermentation was taken out for 0, 10, 24, 36, and 72 hours. The amount of reducing sugars contained in the fermented peel was measured using a pH meter after the peel had been fermented.

Sixth Experiment

After the second experiment, the starch hydrolysates that were obtained were put into a new set of conical flasks. Each flask contained a culture of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* that had been growing for the previous 48 hours after it had been collected. In conical flasks, the temperature was maintained at 32.5 degrees Celsius, and the pH was maintained at 5.0. The fermentation procedure was conducted out for a total of 0, 10, 24, 48, and 72 hours with an inoculum concentration of 6% (v/v). After the fermentation process was complete, the amount of reducing sugar that was still present was measured, and the pH level was determined.

Seventy Experiment

A fresh set of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was collected and introduced to each of the flasks used in the previous experiment three. pH was changed and the temperature was kept at 32.5°C during fermentation. Bacterial fermentation was carried out for 48 hours using a 6-percent inoculum (v/v).

Eighth Experiment

Each of the flasks from the fourth experiment was infused with freshly collected yeast. The temperature of the fermentation was adjusted while the pH was maintained at 5.0. 6% (v/v) was used as the inoculum, and the fermentation process lasted 48 hours.

Ninth Experiment

Except for the sets in the sixth experiment, all other sets of starch hydrolysate were fermented. Each flask was loaded with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* after it was collected. Temperature was kept at 32.5°C and pH was kept at 5.0 during fermentation. Fermentation was conducted for 48 hours with a different inoculum volume and time interval.

Distillation of the obtained mixture

This is the technique used for separating liquid from liquid. Differences in the boiling point of components (components to be separated) are used to separate the mixture. Unlike chemical reactions, this is a physical separation technique. Boiling point differences are also used in distillation. The separated mixture is placed in a distillation kettle and brought to a rolling boil. The vaporization of lower-boiling components will take place first. A distillation head and a condenser are used to condense this vapor. After cooling and liquefying in condenser, the liquid is collected in a flask for further processing. When a flask is filled with low-boiling components, the process begins. Components with lower boiling point begin to evaporate from the pot as distillation progresses. Using a measuring cylinder, each of the samples from the fifth-ninth experiment was distilled and collected at 78°C. Researchers measured the ethanol's concentration.

Calculation of Ethanol Production Percentage

The ethanol concentration was calculated by multiplying the obtained distillate volume by the ethanol density (789g/L), which was done with the use of a measuring cylinder.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sweet potato: A Study in Composition

Table 1. Sweet potato's composition

Sweet potato	Weight (kg)	Percentage %
Sweet potato (before peeling)	6	-
Sweet potato (after peeling)	4	80
Losses due to peeling	2	20

The content of the sweet potatoes both after and before processing is detailed in Table 1. The skin of the sweet potato was peeled off with the help of an abrasion peeling machine. Sweet potatoes weighing 6 kilogrammes were peeled, giving 2 kilogrammes of skin and 4 kilogrammes of flesh. This sample consisted of 80 percent sweet potato flesh and 20 percent sweet potato skin. The sweet potato skin made up 20 percent of this sample. The weight of a sweet potato loses anywhere from 20 to 45 percent of its total mass when it is peeled. This particular sweet potato shed 20 percent of its total mass during the peeling process.

Fig 1: Analytical Study On Sweet Potato Peels

Above Figure depicts the sweet potato peel's chemical composition; the majority of the peel is made up of organic matter (94.4%), while the remaining fraction is made up of reducing sugar (1.22%). The fact that the peel of a sweet potato contains lipids, carbohydrates, sugars, and starch is evidence that the peel also contains a considerable quantity of carbon. According to the research, the sweet potato peel had a higher degree of ash than the meat, with a moisture content of 61.2 percent and a dry matter content of 3 percent to 4 percent. Additionally, the sweet potato peel contained a bigger amount of dry matter. As a result of the more ash content of the sweet potato skin (5.6 percent), the ash content of the sweet potato flesh is only slightly higher (just under 4 percent). The quantity of ash that may be detected in sweet potato peels can be used to determine how mineral-rich they are. The skins of sweet potatoes contain traces of a number of minerals ranging from calcium to phosphorus to iron to zinc include. According to the findings, the high starch and total carbohydrate content in the sweet potato peel, but a comparatively low reducing sugar concentration. The sugar content was determined to be 71.1 percent, 64 percent, and 1.22 percent respectively.

Sugars that are capable of going through the process of fermentation include monosaccharides like glucose, galactose, and maltose. It is necessary to convert the sweet potato peel's carbohydrate content into fermentable sugars in order to extract more ethanol from the peel. This is the reason why reduced sugar content was as low as 1.22% and as high as 60%, respectively, of the starch content. The carbohydrate found in the peel was hydrolyzed with acid in order to convert it into sugars that can be fermented.

Fig 2: The effect on reducing sugar by acid concentration after hydrolysis

The difference in acidity content that can be seen in Figure 3 is the result of the hydrolysis of reducing sugars. The acid hydrolysis was carried out at a temperature of 121 degrees Celsius. According to the graph, the amount of fermentable sugar that was produced grew as the concentration of the acid, but this increase was followed by a drop as the acid concentration climbed. This disparity can be explained by the fact that higher temperatures resulted in the production of less sugar when concentrated acid was used. Because the acid concentrations in 0.2M and 0.5M were lower than in 1M and 2M, they were able to produce higher levels of sugar. This was possible because 1M and 2M contained higher acid concentrations. Because they are more concentrated, hydrochloric acid solutions sugars that may be used for fermentation were less abundant in 1M and 2M temperature of 121 degrees Celsius than solutions of 0.5M and 0.2M.

At 0.5M, the greatest quantity of sugars that may be fermented was discovered.

Table 2. Following the fermentation process, the acid concentration of HCl reduces sugars and pH, reducing the amount of sugar eaten and the amount of ethanol that is produced.

	Molar concentration (M) Of HCL	Reducing sugars after hydrolysis (g/L)	Reducing sugars after fermentation (g/L)	pH after fermentation	Reducing sugars consumed (g/L)	Yield Y (p/s)
1	0.2	25.31	6.53	3.25	18.78	0.26
2	0.5	25.91	6.94	3.36	20.79	0.31
3	1	26.7	6.94	3.91	19.76	1.283
4	2	19.59	6.53	3.92	13.06	0.294

Both the rate at which a microorganism (yeast) consumes sugar and the conditions under which fermentation takes place are given in Table 2, and both of these factors have an impact on the amount of reducing sugar that is left over after fermentation has taken place. The acid concentration influences just the quantity when fermentation occurs; it has no effect on the amount of reducing sugars that are released that are still present after fermentation has taken place. The amount of reducing sugars that are left behind after the fermentation process is what determines the amount of ethanol that can be produced. Whether the conditions for fermentation are not favorable, then it won't matter if there is a significant amount of sugar that can be fermented because that sugar won't be utilized.

Fig 3: The Effect of Time of Fermentation on Ethanol

The synthesis of ethanol is depicted in Figure 4 for a range of different acid concentrations. Fermentation of ethanol took place at 32.5 degrees Celsius with a pH of 5 for 0, 10, 24, 48, and 72 hours. After 48 hours, each of the different acid concentrations produced the largest possible amount of ethanol. The technique allowed us to produce a maximum of 0.2M, 0.5M, 0.5M, 0.0M, 1.0M, and 2.0M of ethanol in a span of 48 hours. This was the maximum amount of ethanol we were able to obtain. Before being employed in this experiment, the yeast had to first go through the lag phase of fermentation, then the log phase, then the stationary phase, and finally the death phase. The amount of biomass, or ethanol, produced by yeast grows whenever a yeast cell divides, and the more sugar yeast consumes, the more ethanol is generated. The lag period happened from zero in the morning until ten in the evening. It took the yeast anywhere from 0 to 10 hours to adjust to the new environment (the flask), and once it did, it began to develop, although it was difficult to observe at first. Yeast cells multiplied rapidly during the hours of 10 and 48, using nutrients from the medium. This time lasted between 10 and 48 hours. Because yeast cell growth speeds up the production of ethanol, this resulted in an increase in the amount of ethanol produced by the yeast. However, after 48 hours, the yeast stopped growing and stayed in its original state. After 48 to 53 hours, the yeast cell development came to a complete end, and by 53 hours, the concentration of ethanol had reduced significantly. This occurred between the hours of 48 and 53. In the 53 hours that followed, there was a decrease in the amount of ethanol that was produced in order to replace ethanol, the ethanol was transformed into metabolic products. Above graph demonstrates that the most ethanol was produced by 0.5M hydrochloric acid after 48 hours when just the conditions required for fermentation were met. The most fermentable sugars, which can be utilized in the synthesis of ethanol, were extracted from the hydrolysate produced by hydrochloric acid at a concentration of 0.5M.

Fig 4: The Effect on Ethanol Production by pH

During a 48-hour fermentation of the sweet potato peels with 0.5M hydrochloric acid, the ethanol output varies with pH as shown in Figure. Batch fermentation was used to examine the impact of fermentation pH on ethanol production while maintaining a 32.50C temperature and a 6% (v/v) inoculum size for 48 hours. Ethanol production began to rise from pH 4.0 up to 5.0, but then began to decline as the pH fell. At a pH of 5.0, the greatest ethanol output was 6.39g/L. This meant that the yeast cell was unable to ingest fermentable sugar and create ethanol in an acidic environment. A slightly acidic and slightly alkaline environment was ideal for the yeast cell's growth. Yeast cells won't multiply in an acidic or alkaline environment.

Fig 5,

Fig 5: The Effect on Ethanol Production by Temperature

After fermenting sweet potato peel for 48 hours with 0.5M hydrochloric acid, Above Figure depicts the temperature-dependent fluctuation in ethanol output that occurred throughout this process. The generation of ethanol was measured for a period of 48 hours, during which time the pH level was maintained at a level of five and the size of inoculum was established at 6% (v/v) of total volume of the fermentation. The temperature was adjusted to be anything between 200 and 400 degrees Celsius. There was no yield at temperatures between 200°C and 240°C. The maximum amount of ethanol was produced when the temperature reached 32.5 degrees Celsius, and then it gradually reduced as the temperature went down. A decrease in the yeast cells' ethanol output and even their denatured state can result from subjecting the cells to higher temperatures. Yeast cells

are unable to grow at temperatures that are either exceedingly low or excessively high. The best ethanol production, 6.39 g/L, was obtained when the temperature was set to 32.5 degrees Celsius.

Fig 6: Ethanol Production Affected by Inoculum Size

As can be seen in Figure above, the size of the inoculum has an effect on the amount of ethanol that is produced. For the purpose of this study, the inoculum concentrations were varied from 5% to 10%, while the temperature and pH levels were held constant at 32.5 degrees Celsius and 5. The inoculum size was increased until it reached its peak at 6% (v/v), at which point it began to decline before beginning to rise again as the inoculum size increased. The number of yeast cells in the fermentation flask was increased so that larger inoculums could be produced (reactor). When a greater quantity of yeast cells was added to the flask, the rate at which ethanol was created increased significantly. The quick consumption of the substrate (fermentable sugars) and subsequent production of ethanol was a direct consequence of the addition of additional yeast cells. The inoculum size was increased to 6 per cent (v/v), which allowed us to attain the best possible ethanol output. Due to a limited supply of nutrients and increased competition for a single system, the ethanol output fell as the inoculum size increased. This was the cause of the decrease. Yeast cells stopped multiplying (reactor).

IV. CONCLUSION

When it comes to the production of bioethanol, temperature, inoculum size, time, and pH all play important supporting roles. As shown by the hydrolysates that were *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* fermented without the lignin being removed, the peel of sweet potato has been discovered to be a desirable feedstock for the production of bioethanol, particularly in countries that produce millions of tonnes of sweet potato each year. This is especially true in nations where the lignin was not removed from the hydrolysates. At 32.5 degrees Celsius, a pH of 5.0, and an inoculum concentration of 6 per cent (v/v), the fermentation process produced the most ethanol after 48 hours. Peel from sweet potatoes, which is typically considered a byproduct that does not contribute value, has the potential to be utilized productively in the production of ethanol.

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